

WORLD LITERATURE. THE GREAT REPRESENTATIVE OF AMERICAN

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Annotation: The article highlights the hard life of Jack London, one of America's brilliant realist writers, and the factors that motivated his formation as a writer.

Keywords: Image, autobiographical image, Golden temptation, social inequality, short story, fairy tale, legend, Indians, Eskimos.

INTRODUCTION

In the current process of globalization, in order to teach foreign languages to the young generation, to develop a system of training specialists who can speak these languages fluently, and in this process, to create conditions and opportunities for them to use the achievements of world civilization and the world's information resources effectively, to develop international cooperation and communication in our country. a number of decisions were made to improve the teaching of languages, especially English.

In a rapidly developing world, international relations, the impact of their lives on each other, relationships in different spheres, exchanges of experience and thought, harmonization and synthesis have reached a higher level than ever before. Any phenomenon can also receive its literal assessment only on a global scale. In literary studies, the principle of comparative assessment of works of national literature into rare examples of World verbal art is also developing.

Consequently, the influence of advanced world literature on Uzbek literature had a significant impact from the end of the 19th century to the beginning of the 20th century. At the heart of the rise of the art of translation and mutual literary relations, socio-political changes, the growth of direct Babi influence through Russian literature, we see mukin. A number of genres were formed and developed in Uzbek literature under the influence of world literature.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

John Griffith Chaney London, a great representative of American literature and one of the brightest representatives of American critical realism, was born on January 12, 1876 in the east of San Francisco, California, in a poor farming family. After he was born, he was named John Chaney. His mother was Flora Wellman, and his father, William Chaney, was an astrologer. But their marriage ended before Jack London was born.

At the end of 1876, his mother, Flora Wellman, married John London, a civil war veteran who was partially disabled. Together with his baby John (Jack London), the young family moves to Oakland, located on the shores of the San Francisco Bay. John Chaney's name is later changed to "Jack London" after his stepfather. They will live there until they finish the London public school. Due to family financial difficulties, London's childhood was spent with difficulties and hard work. He started distributing newspapers at the age of 10, and later, after the age of 13, he left home and started living independently. In 1889, he earned money by working 12-18 hours a day at Hikmot's canning factory. Such long hours of work exhausted the young boy. To get out of this difficulty, London borrows money from his godmother Virginia Prentiss and buys a boat from a shell pirate named Frank and starts doing this business himself. After his

boat is damaged and rendered unusable, London is recruited as a member of the California Fish Patrol.

In 1893, he signed a contract with the ship “Sophie Sutherland” headed for the shores of Japan and paid off his debt by working as a sailor. When he returned, the country was in the throes of the Panic of ‘93 and Auckland was engulfed in labor unrest. In 1894, London left California and went to Washington with unemployed and wealthy people. They live there in groups and work on the street. Because of this, he was arrested in Buffalo, New York and held in the Erie County Jail for 30 days. About the days spent in this detention center, he says in the work “The Road”: “Human treatment was one of the least unprintable horrors of the pen of Erie County. I say “can’t press”; and in fairness I must also say indescribable. They were incomprehensible to me until I saw them, and I was not a spring chicken in the terrible abyss of the ways of the world and human degradation. It would take a deep descent to get to the bottom of the pen in Erie County, and I would skim the surface of things lightly and face-to-face as I saw them there.

After gaining a lot of experience living as a sailor and porter, he returned to Oakland and attended Oakland High School. He wrote several articles for his high school magazine, The Aegis. His first published work was “Typhoon Off the Coast of Japan”, which tells the story of his sailing experience.

In 1895, Jack London became a member of the social worker’s party and began his campaigning activities. He really wanted to get into the University of California at Berkeley. After intensive training in the London summer, he passed the certification exams and was admitted to the university in 1896. After studying for one year, in 1897, he was forced to leave the university due to financial difficulties. London begins to work hard again. He gets a job at a laundry. After that, on July 12, 1897, he and his sister’s husband, Captain Shepard, sailed to the mines in Alaska to search for gold. There, young Jack sees at every turn the terrible injustices of the ruling class society against the lower class society. Like all the men in the gold mines, London could not get enough to eat, and as a result he suffered from several diseases. These diseases bothered him until the end of his life. Jack, caught in the vortex of the “Golden Temptation”, spends several years of his life there. Many of his works about the life of Indians in the Cold North were created based on his life experiences and experiences there. Beginning in 1900, London’s stories about northern tribes and Indians began to be published in the “Northern Stories” collection. In his stories, the author also tells about his trip to the South Sea. After some time, his stories become very popular among the people, and Jack London begins to make a name for himself as a professional writer. Most of his stories are related to the North Sea voyage and belong to one group of Jack’s collection of works. (“South Sea Stories”, “Werewolf”, “Cold Children”).

CONCLUSION

Jack London shows his opposition to social inequality, unfairness and inferiority of people in these unique and bright works. The author contrasts such injustices of people with the conditions of the cold climate and the unique strong character of people who are behind the times. Jack portrays the Pacific people and the uncivilized Indians as strong, innocent, and brave.

London makes them extremely romantic and glorifies their curiosity, bravery and readiness to fight for life. (“The Story of a Man”, “Odyssey of the North”, “White Silence”, etc.). In the story

“White Silence” Jack glorifies those who can brave the cold weather and overcome the snow storms. However, he portrays his characters, the Indians and the gold seekers, as overly individualistic individuals who put themselves above others in any situation. The wisdom, originality, physical superiority, strong will of Hindus can subjugate not only people, but also wild animals. After 1900, London’s stories and works mainly tried to illuminate the lives of ordinary workers who could not fight for their rights.

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